

CURRENT PROBLEMS IN COMPARATIVE LANGUAGE
LEARNING

R.Dauletbaeva

Karakalpak State University, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Thus, the comparative study of languages is used in the field of linguistic typology. These are the main forms of comparative systematic use in linguistic studies.*

Key words: *comparative, languages, linguistic, typology, foreign, grammatical, problems, universal, method, development.*

Due to the growing importance of studying a foreign language, languages other than the native one, in a comparative manner, their in-depth study is necessary. The reason is that any foreign language is acquired on the basis of the native language. The fact that the native language is also given from foreign languages with grammatical changes and different weapons creates significant difficulties for students of national schools.

This is because learners are exposed to completely different grammatical forms than those in their mother tongue. Such conditions create the problems of studying and researching languages of different systems from the comparative-typological point of view and lead to wide interest among linguists.

Wide spread of comparative study of languages of different systems is associated with the name of prof. R.Yu.Barsuk. In the following decades, we will often encounter questions about the similarities and differences in the construction of language, and about the evolutionary processes in this or that branch. A comparison of languages in this pattern is of great service to general linguistics.

Scientists have expressed their opinion about the importance of comparative study of languages. Academician L.V.Sherba is among them. He wrote: "Contradiction of one language with another based on comparison, expressing the same thought or idea in different languages in different ways gives rise to the unknowable uniqueness of a person's thought (idea)".

To the study and research of languages in a typological comparative type: A.A.Azirov, Dj.Buranov, I.M.Grokhova, N.A.Fillipova, A.L.Zelentsky, P.F.Monakhov, K.Qazoqbaev, N.A.Urumbaev, V.G.Gak, N.K.Turniyazov, A.U.Umarov and A.Dzholdoshbekov and several other scientists made a great contribution.

Paying attention to the research on the basis of equalization-comparison of languages, the famous russian linguist V.I.Yartseva writes about it: "Comparison is always used in the knowledge of the researched language, even in studies whose goal is to show a language in a system outside of itself, for example, it is also possible to compare form and content".

Therefore, comparison can be considered as a universal way of researching (studying) language construction. This is a really clear and valid argument, because the comparative method is not only theoretical, but also has a significant practical side. It has great practical benefits for stylists and translators. The materials of this study make a great contribution to the development of grammatical characteristics of words in dictionaries of two languages, and it also creates an opportunity for authors of scientific and practical works to use. In the following periods, many scientific works were created in the field of typological-comparative study of languages of different systems.

Russian linguist academician V.V.Vinogradov also mentioned the necessity of comparative typological study of languages. He writes about this: "In addition to the study of sister languages on the basis of historical comparison, they can be studied in various comparative ways and should be studied in this way".

Therefore, in the present period, the study of languages on a typological-comparative basis has become one of the most important branches of linguistics. The object of his research is not only linguistic typology, but the general structure of the language. It can be used in comparative research and research from the practical side, because according to the academician L.V.Sherba: "The specificity of the native language forces us to look at the first subtleties".

Also, at present, the method of comparative study of the grammatical structure of languages of different systems, which has a significant place in the network of linguistic knowledge as a whole, and whose object of study is also research methods, is developing at a high level.

For example, the study of the comparative typology of the Karakalpak and German languages is not only a method for the development of linguistics, but at the same time, in the practice of teaching the German language in national schools, in the development of the methods of teaching this subject, and in the cultivation of translation works, it is necessary to emphasize the existing languages on a typological-comparative basis. Despite the fact that several problems associated with the comparative typological method have not been resolved, this method is continuously developing with the emergence of new theoretical works.

Despite the importance of the comparative study of the Karakalpak and German languages, this problem has not yet been fully resolved: there is information on this network, but not enough. Among them, E.Kunnazarov "Sopostavitelny analiz sochetaemosti perekhodnyx glagolov nemetskogo i karkalpakskogo yazykov". Nukus, 1980, A.Kurbanbaev "Sopostavitelnaya grammatika nemetskogo i karkalpakskogo yazykov". Nukus, 1989, and others studied.

The reason is that the comparative study of languages on this basis is a theoretical and practical guide for the development and adaptation process of certain grammatical categories of the language, for the preparation of grammars for higher education and school students. Thus, as we mentioned above, researching languages with a comparative-historical method is used not only in the study and examination of languages of different systems, but also in terms of origin.

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